

Tracking a novel cyanobacterium bloom in the Indian River Lagoon, Florida, U.S.A., during the summer and fall of 2020

Stephanie Keller Abbe^{1*}, Karen Henschen¹, Laura Markley¹, Célia Villac¹, Eric Muhlbach¹, Charles Tilney¹, Alicia Hoeglund¹, Yida Gao¹, Autumn Biddle¹, Richard Paperno¹, Larry Johnson², Tom Saam², Jim Torpey², Craig Wallace², Tim Moore³, Malcolm McFarland³, Cheryl Swanson⁴, Katherine Hubbard¹

¹ Fish and Wildlife Research Institute, Florida Fish and Wildlife Conservation Commission, 100 8th Ave. SE, St. Petersburg, FL, 33701, U.S.A., ² Indian River Lagoon Marine Resource Council, 3275 Dixie Hwy NE, Palm Bay, FL, 32905, U.S.A., ³ Harbor Branch Oceanographic Institute, Florida Atlantic University, 777 Glades Road, Boca Raton, FL, 33431, U.S.A., ⁴ Florida Department of Environmental Protection, 3900 Commonwealth Blvd., Tallahassee, FL, 32399, U.S.A.

* corresponding author's email: stephanie.kellerabbe@myfwc.com

Abstract

A bloom of an unidentified nano-sized cyanobacterium (~3-4 μm x 5 μm) was observed in the Indian River Lagoon (IRL) system, Florida, U.S.A. from August through December 2020, causing greenish water discoloration. Enumeration by light microscopy revealed concentrations of $> 10^6$ cells mL^{-1} in the northern and central IRL proper, Banana River Lagoon, and Mosquito Lagoon (maximum of 3×10^6 cells mL^{-1}). Bloom concentrations (2×10^5 cells mL^{-1}) were first observed in the northern IRL and Banana River where it persisted longer than in other basins, but cell abundance rapidly declined throughout the system as water temperatures decreased in December. Inspection of archived samples suggested this taxon had been in the system since at least late June. Bloom development and decline was readily observed by satellite imagery (Sentinel-2, Landsat-8). Cells were round to oblong, often with two or more cells aligned in a chain. Live cells had an elongated aerotope that became inconspicuous upon preservation. Flow cytometry indicated that this cyanobacterium had low chlorophyll *a* and high phycocyanin-like fluorescence. Toxin analysis at five time points between 9/24 and 12/03 returned non-detected concentrations of anatoxin-a and cylindrospermopsin, trace levels of total microcystin-LR in four samples, and saxitoxin in three samples; these positive results are likely unrelated to the cyanobacterium bloom. Direct sequencing followed by PacBio 16S amplicon sequencing revealed a novel cyanobacterial ribotype in bloom samples (i.e., $>75\%$ of 16S amplicons). A complete metagenome assembled genome was retrieved and phylogenetic analysis placed this organism adjacent to *Prochlorothrix hollandica*, although within a clade and tree that encompasses large genetic distances between taxa indicating that specific evolutionary and ecological affinities must be interpreted with caution.

Keywords: coastal lagoon, light microscopy, flow cytometry, remote sensing, cyanotoxins, phylogeny

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7034980>

Introduction

The Indian River Lagoon (IRL) is a shallow (in average < 2 m deep) estuarine lagoon system, consisting of multiple basins, extending 250 km parallel to the Atlantic coast of central Florida, U.S.A. In early September 2020, collaborative sampling intensified in the IRL in response to widespread accounts of green water discoloration with incompatible reports of low chlorophyll. Here we discuss the results from efforts focused on following the progression of the event with satellite imagery, cell counts with light microscopy and flow cytometry, toxin analysis, and the determination of the molecular signature of this nano-sized phytoplankton, soon realized to be a novel cyanobacterium.

Material and Methods

Extensive water sampling was implemented from September 2020 through January 2021, comprising 60 sites at a depth of 0.2 - 1 m (Fig. 1a). From these 60 sites, 13 sites were sampled at least five times. Of these 13, the seven most frequented sites were chosen for flow cytometry and three sites were sampled for toxin analyses on select dates (Fig. 1b). In total, 264 live and/or Lugol's preserved samples were analyzed for cell enumeration by the settling technique, using Nunc® chambers and inverted light microscopy, under 630× final magnification (adapted from Edler and Elbrachter, 2010). Level-1 Sentinel-2 satellite images were obtained from the European Space Agency's Copernicus Open Access Hub. These images were processed with the Acolite (Vanhellemont, 2019) to generate true-color images. Flow cytometry samples were preserved in 0.1% glutaraldehyde and analyzed using an

Attune NxT flow cytometer (ThermoFisher, U.S.A.) equipped with lasers and detectors capable of measuring chlorophyll-*a*-like (488 nm excitation, 690/40 nm emission) and phycocyanin-like (637 nm excitation, 670/14 nm emission) autofluorescence signal from phytoplankton cells. Pearson Excel function was applied to test the linear correlation between light microscopy and flow cytometry cell counts. Toxin analyses were performed using EPA method 8321B (EPA, 2007). A sequence initially generated by direct PCR sequencing, followed by PacBio 16S amplicon sequencing, was subjected to BLASTn and SILVA database searches to identify the most closely related taxa (details in Lopez *et al.*, 2021). Subsequently, Oxford Nanopore shotgun sequencing enabled a robust phylogenetic placement using 33 ribosomal proteins.

Fig. 1. Sampling coverage from September 2020 through January 2021. (a) The smallest circles indicate sites visited only once; larger circles sites were visited 21 to 23 times during this period. (b) Selected sites for flow cytometry and toxin analysis, including site names.

Results and Discussion

Sentinel-2 imagery tracked the large-scale progression of this event from non-bloom conditions back in March, water discoloration and broad spatial coverage of the bloom in September, and the system approaching bloom decline at the end of December (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Sentinel 2 satellite images (<https://www.copernicus.eu/en>) showing peak bloom coverage in September. See text for sequence detail.

The fact that reports of chlorophyll levels in the field were very low to not detected (data not shown) was explained when flow cytometry revealed the dominance of cells with relatively low chlorophyll-*a*-like fluorescence and high phycocyanin-like fluorescence. This result was visually confirmed by epifluorescence microscopy that showed a lack of emission under chlorophyll wavelength excitation (470/27 nm) and cells with a red emission under phycocyanin wavelength excitation (640/30 nm). Based on data from seven sites analyzed at two time points, it was also reassuring to demonstrate early in our monitoring that flow cytometry and light microscopy counts of this

nano-sized alga were within the same order of magnitude and highly correlated (r Pearson = 0.91, $p < 0.001$).

Light microscopy examination revealed an unfamiliar cyanobacterium. Relative to known species, this taxon had unique characteristics based on gross morphology. Cells are round to oblong, approximately 3–4 μm by 5 μm , with a pale translucent green appearance, often seen dividing into chains of two, and up to five, cells (Fig. 3a). Examination of live material indicated the presence of an aerotop, or elongated gas vacuole, that collapsed upon preservation with Lugol's iodine solution; in addition, the cell changed in shape, becoming more capsule-like with more homogenous content (Fig. 3b).

Fig. 3. Unidentified cyanobacterium (a) live and (b) Lugol's preserved material. See text for detailed description.

Bloom concentrations, operationally defined as 2×10^5 cells mL^{-1} , started appearing initially in the Northern IRL and Banana River Lagoon basins with five sites exceeding 1 million cells mL^{-1} . Increased sampling efforts between October and November, with up to 20 samples collected each week, exposed the broadest spatial coverage from the northern Mosquito Lagoon stretching south of Melbourne in the Central IRL, although the highest cell concentrations persisted in the Northern IRL and Banana River basins (Fig. 4). During the last week of December, cell concentrations

dropped to below 10,000 cells mL⁻¹, even in the basins where the bloom had initiated and was sustained in previous weeks.

Fig. 4. Mid-November shows the most expansive spatial coverage and with high cell concentrations throughout.

Light microscopy inspection of available archived samples determined that this taxon had been present since at least June 2020. Bloom levels of this cyanobacterium overlapped with bloom concentrations of a brown tide-forming pelagophyte, *Aureoumbra lagunensis*, at some locations in the Northern IRL and Banana River Lagoon (August and September) and in the Central IRL (late-September to mid-October) (Lopez *et al.*, 2021). The abrupt decline in cell abundance in December 2020 coincided with a decline in water temperature below 20°C (Fig. 5). This indicates that this particular species has a strong affinity for warmer water, a trait shared

with many other cyanobacteria (e.g., Carey *et al.*, 2012).

Fig. 5. Bloom distribution over time and associated water temperature with best fit curve.

Toxin analysis at five time points (9/24 - 12/03) returned non-detectable levels of anatoxin-a and cylindrospermopsin and trace levels of total microcystin-LR in four samples, and of saxitoxin in three samples. These positive results for saxitoxin are likely unrelated to the intense cyanobacterium bloom, since the annually occurring summer bloom of the saxitoxin-producing dinoflagellate *Pyrodinium bahamense* was subsiding in the system (Lopez *et al.*, 2021) at the time of sampling.

Direct sequencing with oligonucleotides cya359F and cya781R (b) was successful in a bloom sample from Parrish Park Boat Ramp, and additional direct sequencing with a combination of specific/universal primers yielded a final contig of 2183 bp (GenBank accession number MW816502) covering most of the 16S rRNA gene, the ITS/5S rRNA region, and a partial fragment of the 23S rRNA gene. The closest BLASTn hit was to an uncultured cyanobacterium with percent identity of 96.9% over 65% query coverage (ITS-region missing), and the best hit to a known organism was to *Prochlorothrix*

hollandica, with a percent identity of 93.5% and 74% query coverage. Subsequent shotgun sequencing and metagenome assembly enabled us to align 33 ribosomal proteins to published cyanobacterial genomes and to generate a more robust phylogenetic tree (Fig. 6), which like the 16S rRNA gene data, indicated a placement adjacent to *P. hollandica* and within a clade that also included *Cyanobium*, *Aphanothece*, *Prochlorococcus*, and *Synechococcus*. However, possible evolutionary and ecological affinities between the cyanobacterium from the IRL bloom and *P. hollandica* must be interpreted with caution since this clade, and the entire tree, encompasses large genetic distances. Further studies of thylakoid arrangement and presence of genes associated with the expression of a particular pigment are needed to resolve taxonomic identity and classification. Assessing the genome of this cyanobacterium is expected to shed insight into the physiological capacities and ecological niche of this species and help understand what factors might have contributed to the development of this large and novel bloom.

Acknowledgements. We would like to thank our partners and the field sampling crews: Community Scientists, FL Atlantic University, Marine Resource Council, FL Dep. Agriculture and Consumers Services, FL Dep. Environmental Protection, St. Johns River Water Management District. Special thanks to Cary Lopez, FWRI, for distribution maps in ArcGIS.

Fig. 6. Phylogenetic placement of the IRL cyanobacterium adjacent to *P. hollandica* based on 33 ribosomal proteins and 3,934 amino acids (PhyML tree, 1000 a-Bayes supports).

References

- Carey, C.C., Ibelings, B.W., Hoffmann, E.P, Hamilton, D.P., Brookes, J.D. (2012). *Water Res.* 46, 1394-1407.
- Edler, L. and Elbrachter, M. (2010). *IOC Manuals and Guides*, no. 55. B. Karlson, C. Cusack, E. Bresnan (Eds). Paris, UNESCO, 13-20.
- EPA (2007). Accessed January 2022. <https://www.epa.gov/sites/default/files/2015-12/documents/8321b.pdf>
- Iteman, I., Rippka, R., Tandeau de Marsac, N., Herdman, M. (2000). *Microbiology* 146, 1275-1286.
- Lopez, C., Tilney, C., Muhlbach, E., Bouchard, J., *et al.*, (2021). *Front. Mar. Sci.* 8, 1737.

Nübel, U., Garcia-Pichel, F., Muyzer, G. (1997). *Appl. Environ. Microb.* 63, 3327-3332.

Rocap, G., Distel, D.L., Waterbury, J.B., Chisholm, S.W. (2002). *Appl. Environ. Microb.* 68, 1180-1191.

Turner, S., Pryer, K.M., Miao, V.P.W., Palmer, J.D. (1999). *J. Eukaryot. Microbiol.* 46, 327-338.

Vanhellemont, Q. (2019). *Rem. Sens. Env.* 225, 175-192.

